

CHARACTERIZATION OF CLINICAL AND IMMUNOLOGICAL PARAMETERS OF PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC FORMS OF PULPITIS WITH PAINFUL SYMPTOMS

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Annotation. Despite the long study of odontogenic facial pain, the clinical and pathophysiologic features of atypical facial pain in pulpitis have not yet been elucidated. Such a study would allow dentists to consider pulpitis pain not only as a symptom of dental disease, but also as a systemic syndrome that affects the nervous system, the patient's psyche, his ability to work and quality of life.

Purpose of the study: to investigate the complex of clinical and immunologic parameters in patients with pulpitis.

Materials and methods of research. 107 patients with facial pain caused by dental pulp inflammation aged from 18 to 64 years were examined. The average age was 36 ± 1.2 years. The bulk of the examined patients (87.9%) were aged from 20 to 49 years, fewer patients were aged under 20 years (3.7%) and after 50 years (8.4%). Facial pain was most often detected on the right side - in 60,7% of cases.

Methods of immunologic research. They included determination of the level of antibodies to myeloperoxidase (MPO) and antibodies to myelin basic protein (MBP) in blood serum by means of immunofemoral analysis (ELISA). For this purpose test-systems of "Navina" company (Russia) were used. The content of myeloperoxidase was determined using monospecific polyclonal antibodies in solid-phase enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay.

The obtained data were subjected to statistical processing on a computer with a Pentium-IV processor using Microsoft Office Excel-2003 software package, including the use of built-in functions of statistical processing.

Results of the clinical study

All 47 patients with pain symptom examined by us needed oral cavity sanitation. The hygienic state of the oral cavity was assessed in all patients using the Fedorov-Volodkina hygienic index.

In all patients the leading complaint was pain symptom of different duration, localization and intensity. With the progression of inflammatory/process in the pulp of teeth the pain increased, became aching and excruciating, localized in the area of projection of the affected dental plexus. The pain covered the tooth, gingiva and alveolar process. In most cases (53.7%) the upper dental plexus was affected. On the background of aching pains, in 19.6% of patients there was an

attack-like intensification of pains lasting from several seconds to 1 minute.

Painful paroxysms occurred with different frequency: from 3 - 4 times a day to 5 - 7 attacks per hour. Pain localization corresponded to the affected dental plexus. Pain was most often localized in molars (61.1%) and premolars (36.1%), less often in canines (0.9%) and incisors (1.9%).

Results of the immunologic study. Immunologic studies revealed a significant increase in immunologic parameters in patients with atypical facial pain compared to the comparison group. The difference amounted to 6.2 times.

The established increase of antibody titers to myeloperoxidase in patients with dental neuralgia indicates the presence of systemic vasculitis in them, as these antibodies are one of the markers of inflammatory damage of small vessels. Dental neuralgia was the result of systemic vascular process, proceeding by the type of vasculitis, caused by allergy to infectious-allergic factors.

Conclusions: Inflammation in the pulp of teeth in the examined patients accompanies not only the pain symptom, but also disorders on the part of the immune, nervous system, manifested in 42.1% of patients with the syndrome of vegeto-vascular dystonia, 24.3% - focal lesions of the brain, combined with dental plexopathy

References:

1. Akbarov, G.R. Dibazol and euphyllin SMT-phoresis in the treatment of facial neuritis at cranial - cerebral trauma [Text] / G.R. Akbarov I Climatic preformed physical factors in the prevention and rehabilitation of patients with bronchopulmonary and cardiovascular diseases. - M., 2021 P. 69- 70.
2. Grechko, V.E. Emergency care in neurostomatology. Izd. 2 [M.: Medicine, 2020 - 256 p.
3. Diagnostic possibilities of magnetic stimulation in facial nerve lesions [Text] / A.A. Skoromets [et al] // Neurological Journal. - Moscow: Medicine, 1997. - № 5. - C. 29 - 31.
4. Erokhina, L.G. Facial pains M.: Medicina. - 2013
5. Zavalishin, I:A. Facial neuropathy // Russian Dental Journal. - M., 2001. - NO. G. - P. 21 -25.

